

ORGANIZATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND RECREATION WORK IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8416158>

ABSTRACT: Based on the analysis of the ideas of various specialists, the article examines one of the urgent problems of our time – the problem of preserving and strengthening health. The article substantiates the position that the problem of forming a culture of health and value attitude to it in preschool children should also become a pedagogical problem.

KEYWORD: Health, healthy lifestyle, public health, health components: somatic, physical, mental, moral.

Preschool age is crucial in forming the foundation of children's health. At the present stage of society's development, the task of educating healthy, harmoniously developed people with high mental and physical performance is being set in a new way. To successfully solve this problem, it is important, as they say, "to take care of health from a young age." There are opportunities for improving children's health in preschool institutions. Throughout the entire period of the child's stay in kindergarten, his health is protected, the body is strengthened, the level of efficiency and resistance to various diseases is increased. Preschool children are inherently very mobile. In countless movements, their natural desire for development is manifested. Being a biological need of a person, movements serve as a prerequisite for the formation of all systems and functions of the body, enriching with new sensations, concepts, ideas. Teaching the correct movements of children is not only necessary, but also necessary. Therefore, one of the main tasks is the proper organization of physical education of children. Reasonable physical education is the basis for the overall development of the child, as it contributes to his normal growth, health promotion and the formation of the psyche. The formation of physical qualities, motor skills and abilities is closely connected with the intellectual and mental development of the child, with the upbringing of moral and volitional personality traits. The main tasks of physical education: protection and strengthening of the child's health, hardening of the body; achievement of full-fledged physical development: harmony of the physique, according to the age of developed functions and adaptive abilities of the body, physical and mental performance; education of moral and volitional personality traits, activity, independence; creating conditions for appropriate motor activity of children; formation of vital types of motor actions: walking, running, jumping, crawling and climbing, throwing, catching and throwing; movements of the arms, legs, trunk, head; constructions and rearrangements; formation of a wide range of game actions; development of physical (motor) qualities: dexterity (including coordination abilities), general endurance, speed and strength qualities, as well as the ability to maintain balance; promoting the formation of correct posture and preventing flat feet; formation of accessible ideas and knowledge about the benefits of physical exercises and games, about basic hygiene requirements and rules;

Education of interest in active motor activity and the need for it. To solve these tasks, all conditions must be present in the kindergarten to ensure a sufficient level of motor activity in classes and walking: an equipped gym, a playground on the territory of the kindergarten, various sports simulators, including hand-made ones, group sports corners, sports equipment. All this contributes to the assimilation of the age program, helps to make classes useful and interesting, and provides an optimal amount of physical activity and a high level of motor activity. Organizational forms of work with children in physical culture in kindergarten are: educational activities; physical culture and wellness work during the day; active recreation; independent motor activity of children; Work with the family. The main type of OD is physical education classes. In order to develop and maintain the interest of children, it is necessary to use different forms of physical education: classical classes (according to the scheme: introductory and preparatory part, main, final parts); gaming sessions (using games: the people, outdoor games, relay races, games, rides, etc.); classes and training type (walking, running, marching exercises, sports games, exercises, climbing, acrobatics, exercise ball, etc.); – story class – a comprehensive (combined in a particular subject, Hiking, orienteering, with the development of speech, with quizzes, etc.); – a rhythmic gymnastics (classes consisting of dance moves); classes in the "Study your body" series (conversations about your body, self-massage training, instilling basic skills in self-care and first aid); thematic classes (with one type of physical exercise); control and verification classes (identification of a lag in the development of the child's motor skills and ways to eliminate them). The number and duration of physical education classes per week are different for young children, younger preschool, middle and older. They are determined by the peculiarities of children's development, the degree of their physical fitness and independence, depend on the distribution of the total budget of time in the day mode. Starting from the second junior group, 3 classes a week are planned. One of them in the senior preschool age is held all year round in the fresh air. Physical culture and wellness work includes: morning gymnastics, outdoor games and physical exercises on walks (morning and evening), physical culture minute. Through morning gymnastics, very special tasks are solved, namely: to "wake up" the child's body, adjust it to an effective way, influence the muscular system in a versatile but moderate way, activate the activity of the cardiac, respiratory and other body systems, stimulate the work of internal organs and sensory organs, promote the formation of Morning gymnastics is also valuable because children develop the habit and need to perform physical exercises every day in the morning. In addition, it provides an organized start to the day in kindergarten, makes it possible to switch the attention of pupils to joint forms of activity. Outdoor games and physical exercises on the walk are carried out both with all children and with small subgroups. It is important that during the day each child takes part in an outdoor game organized by the educator. However, in no case should outdoor games and physical exercises be equated with physical education classes. Their main difference is that the games are held in a more relaxed form, their duration is less. The interests of children are more widely taken into account here, and a variety of types and forms of games are provided. Walking games can be organized at different times of the year. If the whole group participates in the game, it is more expedient to hold it at the beginning of the walk. Games with small groups of children and individual caregivers organize throughout the walk. The purpose of physical exercises (for the development of speed of movement; for the development of dexterity; for the development of strength and endurance) should arouse children's interest in the independent

search for various movements, teach elementary control of their movements. Let the guys just play, and exercises in movements turn into a motor fairy tale, fun fun, relaxed interesting action with an adult, a peer or with everyone together. Physical training minutes (physical training minutes) are held in classes with a mental load. They relieve fatigue and activate children's thinking, increase mental performance. Physical training sessions can be conducted in the form of general developmental exercises, outdoor games, didactic games with movement, dance movements, performing movements to the text of poems, as well as in the form of any motor action and task, but depending on the type of lesson and its program content. Active recreation of preschoolers consists of physical recreation, physical culture holidays and Health Days. All these activities contribute to the improvement of motor skills in children, the formation of their interest and need for physical exercises, the promotion of physical culture among the population. Planning of physical recreation and holidays is carried out taking into account the level of general physical development of children of this group and their motor capabilities. Independent motor activity of preschoolers proceeds under the supervision of a teacher. The content and duration of children's physical exercises and games are determined by the children themselves. The nature of these classes depends on the individual data, preparedness, capabilities and interests of children. Organizing the motor activity of children, it is important to remember about the physiological capabilities and physical health of each child. It is the individual approach that should be most fully and widely used by educators for the organization of independent motor activity of children. It is necessary to arrange the play equipment in such a way that it is accessible to children. One of the means of increasing motor activity in the independent activity of children is motor improvisations to music. Rhythmic movements, stamping, circling in time with the music give the child emotional pleasure. Therefore, it is necessary to strive for music to be played more often in preschool during leisure hours and independent games of children. The regime of children's life, as a form of physical culture and wellness work, includes a Health Day. It is recommended to conduct it at least once a quarter. On this day, the daily routine of the pupils is saturated with active motor activity, independent games, sports competitions, musical entertainment. In the warm season, the whole life of children is taken out into the open air. In the cold season, the stay of preschoolers outdoors is extended as much as possible. On Health Day, walks outside the kindergarten are organized – to the stadium, to the park, to the forest, to the meadow, to the river, lake, to the seashore, etc. In order to carry out successful physical culture and health work, the kindergarten must work closely with parents. Effective forms of organizing physical culture and wellness work with parents are: joint holding of physical recreation, holidays, health days, hiking trips, competitions; open days, where parents have the opportunity to attend morning gymnastics, physical education classes, regime moments; consultations, conversations, recommendations for parents; parent meetings, round tables; demonstration of advanced family education: interviews, exhibitions, meetings with parents, conferences. It is good in kindergarten or group to have a library on physical education for the family: stories, poems on physical education for family reading. The main thing is that they are not imposed, but arouse interest with their novelty, served without stamps, edification and moralizing. The positive effect of physical culture and wellness work is possible only with the gradual, systematic and comprehensive organization of it.

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